

Enhancing operational stability in perovskite solar cells by solvent-free encapsulation method

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The long-term stability of perovskite solar cells is one of the main concerns regarding the upscaling of this technology. In this paper, we develop a simple, fast, and green method to encapsulate perovskite solar cells, maintaining the optoelectronic properties after water immersion. The use of a photo-curable monomer as a sealant offers a fast encapsulation process as well as avoids the need for a solvent that could degrade the perovskite layer. Electrical characterization of the devices (J - V curves and IS) barely shows any changes in the sample's behaviour. In addition, encapsulated samples kept 80% of their initial PCE after the aging test (e.g., ISOS-D-1) as well as after exposure to harsh environmental conditions such as high humidity (>80% RH) and elevated temperature (140 °C). The article presents an insight into the electrical processes after the encapsulation method, paving the way for the development of an efficient method to protect high efficient solar cells.

Introduction

Perovskite solar cells have become a reality as a possible replacement for silicon technology by its impressive progress over the last 10 years.[1] Based on the excellent optical and optoelectronic properties, high carrier mobility, and high absorption coefficients as well as long charge-carrier diffusion length and the possibility of tuning the optical bandgaps, the power conversion efficiency has improved from 3.8% to over 25.5%.[2] Despite the outstanding properties mentioned above, there are still some issues that need to be addressed to upscale and commercialize this technology. Among them, the material instability due to external factors (humidity, temperature, and light intensity) and possible phase segregation induced by an intrinsic degradation entail the major obstacles to broad their applications because of the poorly understood degradation pathways. In this regard, Wang et al.[3] studied the chemical reactions induced by different external factors aforementioned. In particular, the decomposition of perovskite film in the presence of high humidity is mainly ascribed to the hydrolysis of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$. Under such conditions, water molecules easily penetrate the perovskite structure and form an intermediate monohydrate and dihydrate perovskite. Although these intermediates are reversible after dry conditions, water molecules weak the bond between the cation and the PbI_6 , allowing for faster deprotonation of the organic cation.

Although perovskite films resist under operation temperatures (333-383 K), $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ films are more sensitive than their mixed counterpart $(\text{MAPbBr}_3)_{0.17}(\text{FAPbI}_3)_{0.85}$, where MA and FA correspond to methylammonium and formamidinium, respectively. In addition, at temperatures higher than 423 K, the perovskite readily decomposes due to an endothermic reaction into its components PbI_2 , CH_3NH_2 , and HI.[4–6] In addition, the use of Spiro-OMeTAD, also contributes first to absorbing water molecules due to its hygroscopic character[7], and the second temperature above 358 K, induces the gold migration to the perovskite layer.[8, 9]

Those sequential reactions decrease device performance, or in the last term, the complete annihilation of their optoelectronic properties. Another factor to take into account is the instability of high-intensity light illumination.[10] Although its effect could be reduced by the use of UV-light filters, the combination with

temperature or humidity entails the outbreak of the degradation processes.

Therefore, to overcome external instabilities, great effort has been done regarding the fast degradation, such as taking advance of the hydrophobic character of some polymers,[11] mixed perovskite compositions,[12–14] passivation layers[15–17] or novel hole transporter materials.[18, 19] Recently, many groups have succeeded in utilizing the interface engineering strategy to minimize the influence of moisture and improve stability.[20–23] Likewise, many interfacial materials have been investigated, including metal oxides, polymers, and carbon-based materials. As result, intrinsic device stability has been achieved by the reduction in trap-states and consequently an increment of the open-circuit voltage, due to the passivation of the voids and interface imperfections. Nevertheless, those approaches have not reached a simple and solid method to balance high efficiency and long-term stability.

On the other hand, new methods of encapsulation have lately been proposed with the main purpose to avoid the leakage of lead when the perovskite layer is fully degraded.[24–28] Those encapsulation methods should be considered as a complement step to the approaches aforementioned. As a difference from silicon technology, perovskite solar cells where an organic material formed the hole transporter layer in n-i-p configuration, suffer of degradation at temperatures above 363 K. Moreover, perovskite material is also sensitive to a wide variety of polar solvents, which limits the encapsulation materials possibilities. Considering this, few works have been successful in the encapsulation of perovskite solar cell devices and their long-term stability study.

In summary, encapsulation methods can be classified according to the method and the materials used in the process. It is well known for its high sensitivity to light, high temperature, and polar solvents which limits the use of well-established sealants (e.g. based on PIB, Polyurethane, Silicone, and MS Polymer technologies, as well as acrylic and butyl tapes). It has been demonstrated[29] as solar cells encapsulated with a stiffer ionomer, such as Surllyn60[®] or SentryGlas[®] Plus (SGP), severely decreased in performance, mainly due to the heating of the cell at the curing temperature (373 K) of the thermoplastic sealant as well as delamination after temperature cycling, which facilitates the inclusion of water molecules. However, the solar cells encapsulated in softer polymers withstood temperature

cycling and retained above 85% of their initial performance after several temperature cycles. In particular, the combination of a desiccant material and UV epoxy resin exhibited significantly improved stability.[25, 28, 30] Nevertheless, due to intrinsic instabilities, a careful and complicated encapsulation system, developed by employing the combination of a desiccant material and UV epoxy resin, exhibited significantly improved stability.

In addition, to improve long-term stability, some studies focused on the reduction of lead from solar devices. As an example, Jiang et al.[24] demonstrate that the encapsulation method based on an epoxy resin (with self-healing properties) lessens the Pb leakage after simulating a realistic scenario in which perovskite modules are mechanically damaged by a hail impact.

According to the current normative,[31] IEC 61215:2016, samples should pass a series of tests depending on the external inputs, temperature, humidity, or UV exposure. Specifically, the norm is distributed in sequences and each of them contains some stress tests pointing specifically to one of the identified main degradations causes aforementioned.

- ❖ **Sequence A** contains minor conditions to provide basic characterization.
- ❖ **Sequence B** tests hot-spots and outdoor behavior.
- ❖ **Sequence C** combines several stress tests where the modules are first preconditioned with UV light and then subjected to 50 thermal and 10 humidity freeze cycles.
- ❖ **Sequence D** contains 200 thermal cycles.
- ❖ **Sequence E** is the damp-heat test together with the mechanical stability tests (hail test and mechanical load test).

It seems that two points are important for passing the heat damp test and the thermal cycling test. First, a temperature stable architecture is needed, where especially the perovskite composition is important. Here, often MA-free perovskites are used because of the volatility of MA. Second, encapsulation can successfully prevent humidity indicating that humidity stability can be managed with external protective layers.

Thus, heat and light stability may be more challenging for long-term stability because they affect the intrinsic stability behaviour of perovskites.

In this work, perovskite solar cells have been encapsulated by an ultraviolet-cured polymer and characterized to unravel the electro-optical properties. For that, perovskite thin films and full devices were exposed to temperature, high humidity conditions as well as light exposure. Special attention to charging transport under degradation perovskite was taken into account to evaluate the effectiveness of the encapsulation.

Results and discussion

Figure 1a. represents the encapsulation process of perovskite solar devices. Due to the fast kinetics, the curable reaction takes less than 30 seconds, which makes it an optimal method to protect perovskites solar cells. In addition, to avoid possible pinholes facilitating the inclusion of water in high humid conditions, a piece of glass was placed onto the full device

leaving the electrodes free to connect to the sample. Temperature increasing during the perovskite solar cell is expected until values close to 353-363K. For that, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) were used to extract the thermal behaviour of the UV- curable polymer in terms of the variations of the thermal degradation and glass transition temperatures, respectively. According to the DSC thermogram (figure 1b), thermal behaviour is characterized by a glass transition around room temperature (293 K). Figure 1c shows the thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of polyurethane-based UV-polymer. The polymer degradation occurs following mainly three steps: first, residual monomers and physically absorbed solvent cause the first small decomposition (433–553 K), the second step involved the decomposition of the main polymer chains (553–673 K), and finally, the full degradation entails the combustion of the carbonaceous residues (673–723 K). The optical properties of the UV-curable polymer (figure 1d) are following the photoreaction, which occurs at low wavelengths. Even though the polymer and the crystal cover are transparent, they are located on the opposite side of the incoming light, therefore perovskite layer absorbs practically 100% of it.

Not only was the curable polymer observed to have no chemical reaction with perovskite, but it also has a low elastic modulus similar to EVA. This low elastic modulus has an important effect on the delamination process occurred when the samples are exposed to temperature changes (day and night). If a delamination process takes place, the perovskite layer would be exposed to water infiltration by the cavities formed between the glass and perovskite layer. Recently, Kim et al.[32] a very thin layer of PDMS with a synthesized CdSe/ZnS-QD was adopted to prevent the penetration of solvent into PSCs and its UV-induced degradation. Interestingly, the encapsulation of flexible perovskite solar cells enhanced the photovoltaic performance as well as retaining more than 99% of the initial efficiency throughout more than 400 h under ambient conditions.

Figure 1. (a) Visual scheme of the encapsulation process. (b) DSC thermogram, (c) thermogravimetric analysis, (d) UV-vis spectra of the thermoplastic polyurethane-based UV-polymer, and (e) encapsulated device soaked in water.

The absorption coefficient α can be investigated through the Tauc relation. The direct and indirect transitions in the band gap of the material are then obtained by analysing the optical absorption spectrum and applying the following formula:

$$\alpha h\nu = C(h\nu E_g)^n \quad \text{with } \alpha = 2.303A/d, \quad (1)$$

where A and d are the absorbance and thickness of the film, respectively, h is Planck's constant, ν is the incident radiation frequency, C is a constant that depends on the transition probability, E_g is the energy band gap, and $n = 1/2$ and 2 for direct and indirect band gaps, respectively.

Assuming that perovskite possesses a direct bandgap, the optical band gap energy E_g of the perovskite layer was estimated from the intercept of the obtained straight lines at zero absorption. According to figure 2a, encapsulated samples present better stability when samples are exposed to temperatures above the phase transition/ionic migration. Previous studies have indicated the tendency of methylammonium iodide to be removed from the crystal structure when the temperature exceeds 400K. The temperature dependence of the bandgap of the perovskite semiconductor compound is extracted and shown in Figures 2 e) and f). At room temperature, the samples yielded the typical

absorption spectrum of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite between 300 and 760 nm due to the band gap of 1.56 eV. When samples are heated the absorption onset in $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ changes from 780 nm at 298.15K to 740 nm at 423.15K. The bandgap increases linearly as the lattice temperature increases of un-encapsulated devices with a linear coefficient of $1.6 \text{ meV}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$. This behaviour is particularly different from that in most of tetrahedral semiconductors. According to previous work, this effect can be ascribed to the appearance of two bandgaps related to the CH_3NH_3 -ordered and CH_3NH_3 -disordered domains due to a phase transition.[33]

Figure 2. a) Absorbance dependence with temperature of encapsulate perovskite film. b) Absorbance cycling stability of encapsulate perovskite film. c) Absorbance dependence with temperature of un-encapsulate perovskite film. d) Absorbance cycling stability of un-encapsulate perovskite film. e) Bandgap dependence with temperature of encapsulate and un-encapsulated perovskite film. f) Evolution of bandgap after temperature cycling (298.15K-353.15K).

On the other hand, encapsulated devices show also phase transition, but the linear coefficient is reduced to $1.1 \text{ meV}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$. To evaluate if the samples go through an irreversible degradation process, cooled samples (orange line in figure 2 a) and b)) exhibit different values depending on whether they are encapsulated or not. Un-encapsulated samples display an increment of the initial band-gap until 1.62 eV, which can be ascribed to a Pb_2 formation that provokes an enhancement of the E_g . [34]

Figure 2f represents the temperature cycling of the perovskite layer from room temperature (298 K) to average operation temperature (353 K). As was expected, the perovskite layer was not affected when it is heated below 473 K and humidity conditions do not exceed more than 50%RH. Unlikely, a full device includes a variety of layers of different materials nature, which will behave differently according to the external stimulus.

For example, some authors suggest, (ref) that due to the thickness of the metal contact, an infiltration of the metal through the organic layer (usually Spiro-OMeTAD), used as hole extractor, partially affected the final performance of device when we increase the temperature above 355K.

Figure 3. Power conversion efficiency (PCE) evolution with a temperature cycle (320K to 360K) of un-encapsulated device.

In order to evaluate the performance of the un-encapsulated perovskite solar device under a change in the operation temperature, we have inserted a full device inside a climate chamber and varied the temperature from 320 K to 360 K (figure 3). The power conversion efficiency was evaluated continuously while the temperature was increased by a ramp of $1.5 \text{ K}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. According to figure 3, the PCE shows a clear dependence on the temperature as was expected with the optical measurements. Nevertheless, after one cycle (heating and cooling), it can be observed a drop in efficiency of almost 28% from the initial value. As discussed, the temperature will affect not only perovskite material but also other layers such as HTM or metal contact.

According to chemical reactions induced by temperature stimulus, $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{I}$ diffuses out of the perovskite structure, mainly by its attachment with hydrogen bonds to the inorganic part. Besides, $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2 + \text{HI}$ (both in gas form) are produced due to the decomposition of the perovskite structure. Recent studies[35] pointed out the process in which, iodine after the exposure to gamma-ray can favorably react with the ammonia and re-join with the methyl radical to recover $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{I}$; returning to the equilibrium and pushes the reaction leftward, which in turn accomplishes self-healing. Increasing the time of the radicals in the structure will favor the healing process. Bearing this in mind, encapsulated devices were compared with un-encapsulated ones at high temperatures under constant light illumination. The performance after the combination of both factors will give us an idea of the effectiveness of the encapsulation with the UV-polymer.

Figure 4 summarized the evolution of the device performance after 358K and under illumination and standard humidity conditions (45%RH) for 16 hours. The results suggest the success of the encapsulation as it kept above 80% of the initial efficiency. The inset of the figure shows the set-up of the experiment, where a Peltier element was used as a heater to achieve the desired temperature.

Figure 4. Comparison of the evolution of the normalized PCE of encapsulated and unencapsulated devices. A threshold of 80% of the initial PCE is indicated to consider good stability.

Nevertheless, it is well determined that high humidity conditions contribute to the majority degradation of the perovskite solar devices. For that, we have estimated how much affect the encapsulation process and the immersion of the device underwater for a period of time. The characterization through J-V curves (figure 5) reveals barely degradation after the encapsulation step nor after its immersion in water for 5 minutes. If we compare the values of the characteristic parameters extracted from the measurements, open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) did not change considerably, but a drop of 13 mV can be attributed to an increment in the series resistance. The increment of the current density values was supposed to be to a small effect of photo-doping as the same sample was measured in the test. However, the main value affected after the immersion was the fill factor, which decrease from 75.3% to 73.38%. According to the curves, we suggest that this slight drop can be due to a consequence of a lack of contact during the measurement.

Figure 5. J-V characteristic parameter of an un-encapsulated fresh device, after encapsulation and after its immersion in water for 5 minutes.

Figure 6. Comparison of the evolution of the PCE of encapsulated and un-encapsulated devices during their exposure to water vapour. A threshold of 80% of the initial PCE is indicated to consider good stability.

To further investigate the degradation effect of the humidity on devices, we compare the PCE of encapsulated and un-encapsulated devices after its exposure of water vapour (85-90%RH). With this, we can evaluate high humidity conditions as well as high temperature because the vapour is generated very close to the devices. After the exposure for 24 hours (Figure 6), encapsulated devices showed a very good performance as they kept 70% of the initial efficiency. If we compare it with the un-encapsulated device (inset of figure 6), after only 2 hours, it suffered from a drastic poor performance. Consistent with the visual appearance of the devices after the experiment (inset of figure 6), the un-encapsulated device has suffered from a fast deterioration and consequently collapse of the perovskite layer. Furthermore, we extracted the J-V parameters of the encapsulated devices before and after the experiments and compared them (outset of figure 6). Likely, in the constant temperature experiment, we observed an increment of the current density caused by a photo-doping effect. However, it was noticed a high drop in the fill factor of the device (from 71.13% to 51.56%).

A difference between the previous water exposure for 5 minutes and according to the visual appearance of the encapsulated device (inset figure 6), metallic contact seemed to be affected by the water exposure. The series resistance increased from $6.6 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ to $16.6 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$, calculated from the dark I-V curves (Figure S3b), resulting in a drop in efficiency of $\sim 3\%$ from the initial value.

To evaluate if the fill factor drop is caused by a degradation of the perovskite, the carrier density profiling[36] was calculated from the capacitance-voltage measurements in Figure S3a. A fresh, aged (12 months) and un-encapsulated sample are shown to be used as references.

The profiling distance (Figure 7) is not affected for the encapsulated sample, even after being exposed to high humidity, which is a good indicator of a low quantity of free

charges in the absorber. Conversely, in the aged sample, a residual capacitance does not allow for deeper profiling than $0.25 \mu\text{m}$, even if the perovskite layer is thicker.

The aged sample reaches minimum values in the order of 10^{16}cm^{-3} , with values higher than 10^{18}cm^{-3} in the interface, suggesting an increase of defects due to exposure to air. A value lower than 10^{16}cm^{-3} is considered to be a good enough defect density to avoid most of the bulk recombination. Fresh and encapsulated samples show a carrier density from 10^{15} to 10^{16}cm^{-3} along with the absorber thickness, indicating high quality and lack of defects in perovskite. It is observed an increase that approaches 10^{17}cm^{-3} close to the junction, which is caused by an increase of defects in the interface. Therefore, is clear that the encapsulation process is not affecting the quality of the absorber material and is effectively protecting it against moisture exposure, with most of the losses produced in the metallic contacts.

Figure 7. Carrier density distribution along the device profile.

Extreme conditions such as immersion in water of encapsulated samples will demonstrate its efficacy in an easy and fast approach. Figure 8 (inset) represents the experiment setup,

where an encapsulated full device is immersed and illuminated constantly during the measurement. Normalized PCE and Open circuit voltage are parameters taken to assess the evolution of the cell performance at MMP as it is shown in figure 8. The sample presented considerable stability for 17 hours retaining almost 100% of the initial efficiency followed by a drastic drop in voltage. Nevertheless, the failure was due to a lack of metallic contact. It demonstrates as the encapsulation is quite effective but more effort must be addressed to improve the encapsulation of the metallic contacts, as the polymer possesses an insulating character.

It has been shown as the solvent-free encapsulation process has no chemical interaction with the perovskite layer. However, the effectiveness of the encapsulation in harsh conditions can be studied analysing recombination processes in the device. In particular, by utilizing Impedance Spectroscopy (IS) it is possible to differentiate various resistive and capacitive processes occurring in the device either on interfaces or in the bulk on the different time scales, including charge transport, recombination and slow ionic processes (at low frequencies) to which hysteretic behaviour has been lately associated.

Figure 8. Evolution of the PCE of encapsulated devices during their immersion into water.

IS measurements were performed in order to obtain information about various internal processes occurring in the complete perovskite device at various operation conditions and separate interfacial and bulk processes.

Figure 9. (a) Nyquist plot at 0.98V and Capacitance vs voltage. (b) Low frequency vs voltage extracted from the Capacitance–frequency spectra from IS of fresh, after the encapsulation process and after 5 min immersion in water samples.

As shown in Figure 9a, the impedance spectra obtained were characterized by two semicircles. However, in the sample after

the water immersion, those two signals are not well defined which means that different processes are linked. As those

processes are very close in time, there are certain difficulties of estimating the exact values of time constants and resistances for each process, individually. In order to understand the recombination kinetics under different optical excitation wavelengths, the Nyquist plot of impedance spectra (Figure S1) was examined. According to the previous J-V characterization, where slight variation between the fresh and the encapsulated sample was observed, impedance measurements present almost the same response, confirming the inexistence of a detrimental chemical interaction during the encapsulation process.

Figure S2 shows the electron recombination resistance extracted by fitting the impedance response under illumination to a simple $-R_s-(R_1,CPE_1)-(R_2,CPE_2)$ - equivalent circuit, where a constant phase element (CPE) replaces an ideal capacitor to obtain a better fitting. Moreover, it is well known that capacitance in perovskite solar cells is in general dominated by the geometrical component, which can be expressed by the following formula; $C_g=\epsilon\cdot\epsilon_0\cdot A/d$, where ϵ is the dielectric constant of the perovskite, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, A the effective contact area and d is the thickness of the depletion width. Figure 8a (outset) shows that the capacitance extracted from the high-frequency component is constant to the applied voltage, which is in accordance with a geometrical nature. Also, we can observe as a fresh sample was in the same order of magnitude as the sample after the encapsulation process. However, after the water immersion, the sample presented a higher capacitance value, which is in agreement with the lower recombination resistance.

Figure 9b, represents the general response of the frequency-dependent capacitance for the fresh, encapsulated, and degraded devices respectively. According to the literature, a certain specific polarization process is associated with a plateau in the graph. As we have aforementioned, at different frequencies, we can observe various processes taking place inside the devices. At high frequencies range (10^6 Hz to 10^2 Hz), a plateau is observed which is attributed to a dielectric polarization in the bulk of the perovskite. Nevertheless, at low frequencies (0.1 Hz to 1 Hz), ionic motion and charges accumulation at the ETM interface are associated.[37]

According to Zarazua et al.[38] from the exponential correlation of the capacitance at low frequency and voltage, the ionic motion can be evaluated. The outset of Fig. 9b depicts the linear dependency of the capacitance extracted at a low frequency for the voltage. From the slope, the β -parameter, and consequently the ideality factor (n) can be obtained as $n=1/\beta$. Table 2 summarized the β -parameter and the ideality factor of the samples.

Figure 10. Bode plot extracted from IS of fresh, after the encapsulation process and after 5 min immersion in water samples. Dash lines represent the deconvolution of the immersed sample where new processes are identified.

Table 2. Ideality factors for the studied solar cells extracted from impedance spectroscopy.

Sample	Slope	β -parameter	Ideality factor
Fresh	26.7	0.7	1.42
Encapsulated	22.3	0.58	1.72
Immersed	18.46	0.47	2.12

In fresh and encapsulated samples, the ideality factor was close to $n=2$ indicating a trap-limited recombination mechanism, but after immersion, the mechanism changes as evidenced by the significant variation of the ideality factor. Previous research studies[39] suggested that ideality factor $n>2$ indicated a combination of different recombination processes with a high contribution of the surface resistance at high injection mode, which can be attributed to a degradation of the metallic contacts in our case.

Focusing on the effect of the water immersion in the device, plateaus at high frequencies are in the same order, for the fresh and degraded devices. However, a new polarization process in the range of (10^2 Hz to 10^3 Hz) was found at mid frequencies after water immersion. Figure 10 represents the bode plot extracted from IS of fresh, after the encapsulation process and after 5 min immersion in water samples. Alike the fresh and the encapsulated sample, after 5 min immersion sample showed a widening of the peak at high frequencies and a new process at medium frequencies. When the spectra is de-convoluted, two processes can be identified at high frequencies (Peak 1 and 2) and a new one at 10^3 Hz (Peak 3). In previous research,[40, 41] possible charge accumulation at the HTM/perovskite interface was suggested to be the cause of high frequencies processes, and peak at medium frequencies was ascribed to perovskite degradation.

This degradation process observed by spectroscopy techniques has slight importance (at least in short term) when J-V curves are measured. In particular, the evolution of the PCE of encapsulated and un-encapsulated samples was examined. As

Figure 11 shows, encapsulated samples after the immersion for 5 minutes underwater, were periodically measured. Samples were kept at room temperature, 40% RH, and under dark conditions.

Un-encapsulated samples suffered from a drastic drop in efficiency due mainly to a decomposition of the perovskite layer when they were exposed to water immersion. On the other hand, encapsulated samples kept almost the same PCE even after 30 days of water immersion. Nevertheless, aging processes took place with time due to a lack of proper encapsulation in the metallic contact area and lateral side of the device. Samples kept 50% of the initial PCE over one year of the water immersion, demonstrating the improvement of long-term stability after the encapsulation process.

Figure 11. Evolution with the time of the power conversion efficiency of samples encapsulated and un-encapsulated after the water immersion.

Conclusions

Independent of the perovskite composition, which influences the performance of the solar cells, they fail when the device is exposed to harsh conditions such as high humidity or temperature.

Additionally, perovskite suffers from high sensitivity in the presence of a wide variety of solvents, which limits the use of resins for encapsulation of solar cell devices. In order to improve stability, an encapsulation solvent-free procedure is required. Although great efforts have been proposed lately in this direction, it is not sufficient. In order to contribute to improving long-term stability, a UV-cured polymer has been successfully implemented as a sealant agent to encapsulate solar cells.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the encapsulation, samples were exposed to harsh environmental conditions (*e.g.*, high humidity, high temperature, and light). Results indicate that the use of the UV-polymer has no chemical interaction and therefore no influence on the opto-electronic properties of the perovskite. Additionally, after fast degradation experiments under high humidity conditions, encapsulated devices maintain 80% of the initial PCE over 20 h. Remarkably, devices measured

following ISOS-D-1 were stable for 12 months after their immersion in water for 5 min. The good performance of polymer + glass approach is ascribed to the impediment to escape volatile gaseous degradation products (*i.e.*, MA or HI), shifting the reaction equilibrium toward the perovskite. However, electrode contacts seem to be one of the critical aspects to be addressed in order to avoid an increment in the series resistance. After impedance spectroscopy studies, a certain specific polarization process was observed in the encapsulated sample that was immersed in water, indicating recombination processes at the interfaces. However, charge density was not affected after water vapour exposure for 24 h. Accordingly, we suggest that the UV-encapsulation is a promising technique as it also protects the perovskite layer against ionic migration and avoids a collapse in the crystal structure. This work brings this technology closer to the standards for industrial applications.

Experimental

Materials and methods

PbI₂ and CsI chemicals were procured from TCI and used without further purification unless otherwise mentioned. MABr, PbBr₂ and FAI were obtained from Dyesol and 2,2',7,7'-tetrakis(*N,N*-di-*p*-methoxyphenylamine)-9,9-spirobifluorene (Spiro-OMeTAD) was acquired from Merck KGaA.

Solar Cell Device Fabrication

PSCs were fabricated on FTO (NSG10) substrates previously cleaned by a sequential treatment in the ultrasonicator bath in a 2% Hellmanex solution, acetone, and isopropanol, followed by UV ozone treatment for 20 min. The samples were then heated to 500°C and a compact blocking layer of TiO₂ was deposited onto the FTO glass substrate by spray pyrolysis, using a dilution 1/19 mL of titanium (IV) diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) solution in ethanol keeping them for 30 min. Once samples achieved room temperature, a mesoporous dispersion of TiO₂ nanoparticles (30 NRD from Dyesol) in ethanol was spun-coated at 2000 rpm (1000 rpm·s⁻¹ acceleration) for 30 s, followed by a progressive heating step till 500°C for 30 min. Stoichiometric precursor solutions (1.25 M) were prepared, by mixing MAI (Sigma-Aldrich) and PbI₂ (TCI) in *N,N'*-dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and kept under stirring at 70°C overnight in order to dissolve completely PbI₂. The perovskite and HTM films were prepared inside an argon-filled glove box under moisture and oxygen-controlled conditions (H₂O level:1 ppm and O₂ level:10 ppm). The perovskite layers were fabricated by using a two-step spin-coating process, the first step at 1000 rpm for 10 s; and the second step at 3500 rpm for 30 s. During the second step, 120 μL of chlorobenzene were poured onto the films 8 s prior to the end of the program, and then substrates were annealed at 100°C for 40 min. When samples were cooled down to room temperature, Spiro-OMeTAD was then spun coated at 4000 rpm for 30 s by dissolving 72.3 mg of Spiro-OMeTAD in 1 mL of

chlorobenzene; 28.8 mL of 4-tert-butylpyridine was added to the solution as dopants. Finally, 70 nm of gold was deposited by thermal evaporation.

Encapsulation process

Polyurethane acrylate (PUA) photo-resin SPOT-E™ (SPOT-A Materials®) was selected as the UV curable polymer encapsulating material. The encapsulation process was carried out by dropping a certain amount of the photo-resin onto the perovskite solar cell and covering it with a piece of thin glass (500nm) with a slight overlap with the metallic contacts. Samples were exposed under UV light for 1 minute to complete the polymerization reaction.

UV-polymer characterization:

The thermal behaviour of the samples was evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) in a Mettler Toledo TGA/SDTA851 instrument. Measurements were performed from room temperature to 800 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹ under an air atmosphere. For each sample, degradation temperature (T_{deg}) and temperature of the maximum degradation rate (T_{max}) were obtained from the first derivative peak.

The glass transition temperature (T_g) was evaluated by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) For that, it was performed two successive scans under a nitrogen atmosphere from -50 to 250 °C at 20 °C·min⁻¹ and from -50 to 150 °C at 20 °C·min⁻¹, respectively. Measurements were carried out using a DSC 822e from Mettler Toledo. The glass transition temperature was extracted by the extrapolated onset of the baseline shift.

Film Characterization:

Optical properties of perovskite films were studied by Cary 60 UV-Vis spectrophotometer with a Peltier thermoelectric module in the range of temperature 298-363K.

Device Characterization:

Current density–voltage (*J*–*V*) curves were recorded using an Oriel solar simulator (Newport) producing 1 sun AM 1.5 (1000 W·m⁻²) 3A sunlight. Current–voltage curves were measured in air with a potentiostat (Keithley 2604). *J*–*V* measurements were performed at 100 mV·s⁻¹ scan rate (pre-sweep delay: 10 s) and a black metal mask (0.16 cm²) was used over the square solar cell active area to reduce the influence of scattered light. Long-term stability measurements at MPP were performed with in-house made LabVIEW software for a micro-amperimeter Keithley 6487. The software tracks the maximum power point by the perturbation-observation method of the voltage.

The capacitance–voltage measurement was measured using a Biologic potentiostat. The measurements were performed under dark, with a frequency of 100 kHz, an AC voltage of 50 mV, in a range of applied DC bias from -1.2 V to 1.2 V. The

carrier density profiling was calculated using the equations 1 and 2.

$$x_d = \epsilon_0 \epsilon \frac{A}{C} \quad (1)$$

$$N_D(x_d) = -\frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon C}{q x_d^2} \left(\frac{dC}{dV} \right)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Where x_d is the profiling distance, ϵ is the dielectric constant of the perovskite, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, A is the active area, C is the series capacitance, N_D is the carrier density in the absorber, q is the electron charge and V is the DC applied voltage.

Impedance spectroscopy (IS) measurements were carried out by altering the positions of the Fermi level with a white LED source. During the measurements, samples were kept inside a faradaic chamber to avoid external interferences. A 20 mV perturbation in the range 2 MHz – 1 mHz was used to obtain the spectra. After measurement, data were fitted by Z-view software and analyzed in order to extract characteristic parameters of the cells.

Author Contributions

Manuel Salado, sample preparation, electro-optical characterization, experiment design, data analysis, results discussion, manuscript preparation. **David Payno**, spectroscopic experiments, data analysis, revised manuscript. **Shahzada Ahmad**, discussion and revised manuscript.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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